

DUN LAOGHAIRE HARBOUR FERRY TERMINAL DEVELOPMENT

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SYNOPSIS

This paper describes design and construction aspects of Dun Laoghaire Harbour Ferry Terminal Development. The project was required primarily to cater for the revolutionary High-speed Sea Service catamaran craft to be introduced for the first time on the Dun Laoghaire - Holyhead route. The scheme design and construction involved a unique blend of civil, structural, mechanical and electrical engineering. This paper is primarily concerned with the civil and structural engineering features.

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1. INTRODUCTION.

1.1 Dun Laoghaire Harbour.

Dun Laoghaire Harbour has a significant place in the infrastructure of Ireland's capital. Designed by engineer John Rennie and built in the 1820s it initially served the purpose of providing a refuge for ships unable to reach Dublin during winter gales. Vast quantities of granite were quarried in Dalkey and transported to the Harbour by a specially constructed railroad. The completion in 1859 of the Carlisle Pier, the new Mail Packet terminal, brought the Harbour construction work to an end, with a final cost of £1 million.

Dun Laoghaire is the major sea passenger entry port in the Republic of Ireland, with approximately 1.2 million passengers and 205,000 cars passing through the port each year. Dun Laoghaire also handles about 35,000 freight trucks annually through its ro-ro facilities. In the 1960s terminal facilities on the Carlisle Pier were extended and St. Michael's Pier was built, as part of continuing development in the Harbour as shown in Figure 1.

The Harbour is of major importance in the town of Dun Laoghaire. It accommodates a wide range of uses and generates significant employment in the locality. It is known internationally as a sailing centre and is host to four yacht clubs with some 550 swinging yacht moorings within the Harbour itself.

In 1990 the Minister for the Marine appointed an Interim Harbour Board to assist him in aspects of Harbour management and development. The Board prepared and published a Development Plan for Dun Laoghaire Harbour in 1992 which provided for the parallel development of leisure and commercial activities in the Harbour. With respect to the latter the Plan endorsed the continued use of the Harbour by the Commissioners of Irish Lights and the concentration of all shipping activities on St. Michael's Pier.

1.2 The High-speed Sea Service.

In 1993, Stena Line announced the development of a new high speed ferry, called the High-speed Sea Service (HSS). The introduction of this vessel means that for the first time there will be a high speed ferry capable of carrying not only passengers and private cars but trucks and coaches as well. Stena Line announced that the first vessel of this

kind would operate on the Dun Laoghaire to Holyhead route. They had already test marketed the high speed concept on the route with the successful introduction of the smaller Sea Lynx catamaran in 1993.

The HSS introduces a new thinking to the achievement of economies of scale and increased capacity by means of increased frequency of sailing rather than by the introduction of increasingly large vessels. The traditional multi-purpose ferries have a cruising speed of about 20 knots. With the HSS the time taken for a single crossing from Dun Laoghaire to Holyhead will be reduced to 99 minutes, at a cruising speed of around 40 knots. Allowing approximately 30 minutes turn-around time at each port, 5 complete round trips can be achieved daily.

The HSS has a capacity of 1500 passengers and 375 private cars, or 50 trucks with 100 private cars. The ferry is 124m long with a 40m beam permitting all vehicles to load and unload from the stern. In terms of dead-weight tonnage, the HSS is about 5 times that of the largest high speed ferries currently on the seas.

1.3 Programme Constraints.

Following agreement with Stena, the Department of the Marine and the Dun

Figure 1 - Harbour Layout

Laoghaire Harbour Board proceeded to draw up a scheme for development of Dun Laoghaire Harbour to facilitate the new HSS ferry service with a scheduled commencement date of 1st May 1995.

The programme for the project was onerous and included the following principal time constraints and milestones:

- Initiation and execution of Public Consultation Process, Preparation of Planning Application Documentation and Environmental Impact Statement. - 22nd Dec., 1993.
- Preparation of Tender Documentation for Project along with pre-selection of Contractors. - 20th May, 1994.
- Tender Submission. - 17th June, 1994.
- Main Contract Commencement. - 25th July, 1994.
- HSS Trial Docking. - 20th March, 1995

- Commencement of HSS Service. - 1st May, 1995.

1.4 Consultant's Appointment.

Following a formal selection process the Minister for the Marine appointed a multi-disciplinary team of Consultants to design the new ferry terminal facilities and to manage the project through to completion. The team was led by P.H. McCarthy & Partners, Dundrum, Dublin, in association with Posford Duvivier, Consulting Engineers, Peterborough, UK and Burke-Kennedy Doyle & Partners, Architects, Dublin. The appointment was made on 10th November 1993 and work commenced immediately.

2. SCHEME PLANNING.

2.1 Functional Requirements.

The design brief called for the provision of a new state of the art passenger terminal which would provide modern facilities for ferry passengers. A new bankseat was to be constructed to accommodate a revolutionary HSS linkspan and to allow for safe and efficient movement of vehicles and

passengers on and off the ship. In addition new vehicle standage facilities were required for orderly and optimum marshalling of vehicles embarking and disembarking so as to ensure a 30 minute turnaround time for the HSS. Car parking space was required for users of the new terminal. Civic and environmental requirements were to be met by a sympathetic treatment of the new development which was to add to the Dun Laoghaire sea front and its immediate surroundings. Finally, the port at Dun Laoghaire was to be kept fully functional at all stages throughout the construction of the project.

2.2 Environmental Impact Study.

The 1992 Dun Laoghaire Harbour Development Plan identified 'a very real concern for the physical and built environment of the Harbour from the environmental and visual perspective. All development should meet the highest standards of exacting environmental impact assessment'. Under the provisions of the Environmental Impact Assessment Regulations, SI 349 of 1989, any modification of a port which would increase its traffic handling capacity by 20% or more would require an

Figure 2 - Site Layout

Figure 4 - Section Through Cope Beam

advance the scheme in the traditional procurement route of detailed design and tender using admeasurement contracts. The Department had completed a Harbour-wide site investigation programme in 1993 and it was possible to supplement existing data with a small number of site specific boreholes. Accordingly, detailed design could advance apace once planning permission was received. It was decided to complete the detailed design concurrently with the planning appeal process.

As the existing St. Michael's Terminal Building was to be part-retained and extended it was essential that the pier supporting structure was adequate. A detailed study of the pier was carried out during the initial design period by an Engineer diver. The pier was supported on 1m dia. piles/columns cast using the 'Binoto' method. Significant deterioration and spalling had occurred on many of these. Accordingly, a repair strategy using permanent GRP liners and sand/cement grout was adopted for 35 of the worst columns. Following select list tendering the specialist contract was let to Balvac Whitley Moran, Derbyshire, UK in March '94 so as to be complete in advance of the main contract works. The less affected piles are to be permanently repaired on a phased basis in the future.

3.2 Tender Process for Main Contract.

The tendering process was to comply fully with EU Council Directive 90/531/EEC, also known as the Utilities Directive. It was decided that the optimum method of procurement of the project was to invite applications from Contractors for inclusion in a tendering short-list. A Contractor pre-qualification notice was published in the OJEC in March 1994, which resulted in receipt of 16 applications. A total of 6 Contractors were selected and issued with full tender

documents on 20th May, 1994. An advance issue of general information had been issued to tenderers 2 weeks previously and all 6 had confirmed their intention to submit a tender.

Pre-qualified Contractors were allowed 4 weeks to prepare and submit tenders. This short period was required to ensure adherence to the overall project programme.

3.3 Contractual Relationship.

In late July 1994 Ascon Ltd. was appointed as Contractor for the main civil contract. The contract comprised all marine, heavy civil engineering and Terminal Building works. This work was to be substantially completed for the arrival of the HSS in 40 weeks. Ascon undertook the main civil and marine engineering work, with its subsidiary company Rohcon carrying out the construction of the Terminal Building itself.

Specialist packages in the main contract were included as nested sub-contracts. It was the intention that all these would become domestic sub-contracts by negotiation with the selected main Contractor. Following representations by specialist sub-contractors it was agreed that tenders for certain individual items would be submitted to the Consultants a week in advance of the main contract tender due date. The Consultants then selected the appropriate specialists and advised the main contract tenderers accordingly. This applied to mechanical, electrical, cladding and roofing packages. A sheet pile order was placed in advance by the Department in order to secure a rolling slot for the long lead time Larssen 6 piles. The contract was subsequently novated to Ascon Ltd. following their appointment under the terms of their contract.

3.4 Contractor's Programme.

The Contractor's programme was extremely tight particularly as full access to the building works was dependent on the completion of the reclamation works. The work was organised as separate civil and building operations under the control of the site based Project Director. Accordingly autonomy was delegated to site ensuring fast and efficient communication and action. The marine based operations were round-the-clock and highly dependant on weather. The building works represented the overall project critical path due to the critical interdependency and complexity of building services coupled with the linear nature of the building itself.

The construction of the HSS over-ran its original programme in the ship yard in Ravina, Finland, due to shortage of aluminium welders with the result that its delivery to the UK was delayed until February 1996.

The Contractor however continued working to the contractual programme and substantially completed his contract with a 5 week over-run. At peak some 250 personnel were employed on site.

A smaller contract for ancillary building works was awarded to Ascon Ltd. following competitive tender in September 1995. This work is scheduled for completion in April 1996 and includes the Motorists Facilities and Vehicle Turning Out Building together with the Porte Cochere and promenade.

4. CIVIL AND MARINE WORKS.

4.1 Ground Conditions.

The ground conditions within the vicinity of the site in Dun Laoghaire Harbour were determined from the boreholes put down by Irish Geotechnical Services Limited.

The local solid geology was identified as mottled grey and white, medium to coarse, slightly to locally moderately weathered granite. Overlying the granite across the whole site is glacial till, occurring predominantly as a very stiff to hard over consolidated grey/black silty, sandy and gravelled clay. The glacial till head varied with some local dips and troughs but the trend is a shallow dip towards the north and east. Within the glacial till irregular layers or lenses of integral uniformly graded gravels occur. The gravels can range up to cobble or boulder size towards the base of the glacial till.

The superficial deposits comprise a variable sequence of very soft estuarine clayey silts, overlying sandy silts and silty sands which tend to become coarser with depth. The thickness of the

superficial deposits varied between 0m and 4m thick.

4.3 Harbour Wall.

4.2 Anchored Sheet Pile Walls.

The north and east sides of the reclamation area are retained by steel sheet pile walls with tie rods to anchor walls set in the fill. The retained height varies along the length of the wall but averages about 14 metres.

The retaining wall on the east side of the reclamation area is adjacent to the west side of St. Michael's Pier. During the planning stage consideration was given to including St. Michael's Pier within the filled area, but the need to maintain ferry operations at Berth 4 on the east side of the Pier and the requirement to allow access to the cased concrete piles supporting the Pier for future inspection and maintenance led to the adopted arrangement. St. Michael's Pier is founded on vertical cased concrete piles with few raking piles and therefore has a limited lateral load carrying capacity. Since much of this capacity is required to resist the mooring loads from ferries on Berth 4, it was decided to support the retaining wall independently of the Pier. A construction joint is provided between the concrete capping beam and the edge beam on the Pier as shown in Figure 4.

In order to reduce pressures on the retaining wall, silt was dredged out along the line of the wall and a continuous filter drain with weepholes was provided. The stage by stage construction sequence for the wall was fully specified in order to limit stresses in the completed wall and to prevent overloading of the adjacent pier.

The steel sheet pile wall on the north side of the reclaimed area forms part of the linkspan bankseat as described below. The wall in this area has a greater retained height and is therefore anchored by tie rods at low water level and by the bankseat structure. The vertical loads from the bankseat are supported by a series of box piles forming part of the steel sheet pile wall and by tubular steel piles behind the wall.

The west side of the reclaimed area is retained by a mass concrete gravity wall founded on a rock embankment as shown in Figure 5. The outer face of the embankment is armoured with rock to limit wave damage and to reduce wave reflection.

During the planning stage considerable ingenuity was used to develop a design that satisfied both the visual requirements stated by the Harbour Board and harbour users, the cost constraints and the requirement to minimise road transport of materials. A vertical faced retaining wall would have caused complete reflection of waves and would have worsened wave conditions within the Harbour. A rock armoured rubble mound would have been visually unacceptable due to its perceived litter retaining propensity and the required slope and toe would have taken up more valuable space for moorings. In addition the top of the wall provides a public promenade along the west side of the ferry terminal and therefore a suitable edge feature was required.

The line of the wall in plan is largely decided by the shape of the vehicle marshalling area but a curved line has been provided to minimise wave convergence.

The silt beneath the rock embankment was removed by dredging before placing the rock core. Some consideration was given to leaving the silt in place but this plan was rejected due to the likelihood of increased settlement, the possible displacement of silt causing shallowing of the Harbour adjacent to the wall and the penetration of the core material into the silt.

The rock core, rock underlayers and rock armour were obtained from Arklow, County Wicklow. The rock core was delivered and placed by a flat top barge. The underlayers and armour were delivered on a smaller flat top barge and placed by grab using a crane from the reclaimed area, both during and after construction of the gravity wall. The delivery of rock by sea was a specific

requirement of the EIS in order to minimise construction road traffic in Dun Laoghaire.

The gravity wall was designed as a blockwork wall, which provided a cost-effective structure and a visually compatible appearance using featured joints between the blocks. These joints reflected the masonry construction joints in the existing East and West Piers. The design also allowed for some settlement of the underlying embankment and soils. The design envisaged that the mass concrete blocks would be precast off-site during the initial dredging and rock placing phase, delivered on a barge by sea and placed using the same crane that would place the rock armour. However, the Contractor proposed an alternative in-situ concrete design constructed inter-tidally from the fill area. The fill was retained by a temporary sand bund while the wall was constructed. The featured joints were retained in the in-situ concrete structure.

The wall is topped by an in-situ reinforced concrete capping which is shaped to reduce wave overtopping. The security wall runs behind the public promenade and has been designed to withstand the impact of overtopping waves. At the north end the security wall is formed by the outer wall of the motorists' building and this wall and the foundation of the building are also designed for impact from extreme waves.

4.4 Reclamation Operation.

During the planning stage several sources of fill material were considered. The requirement to limit road transport of materials and cost constraints led to a decision to use marine dredged fill. The nearest source of sand fill was the Burford Bank in Dublin Bay but there would be some environmental impact associated with removing material from the Bank, leading to possible delays in obtaining licences, and the sea transport operation would be relatively expensive.

The soil properties of the sea bed material in the Harbour were reviewed and the silty sands underlying the relatively thin layers of silt in the fairway area were identified as being suitable. The silty sands consisted mainly of fine sand with varying amounts of silt. However previous experience of dredging and filling with similar estuarine deposits had shown that a high volume dredging method would result in satisfactory mixing and a reduction in the silt content of the placed material. Therefore an appropriate method of dredging was specified with target fill material properties.

In the case of the Harbour wall some consideration was given to leaving the existing silt in place within the

Figure 5 - Section Through Harbour Wall

reclamation area. However since the silt was up to 4 metres thick and the silty sand fill and the underlying soils would result in large settlements of the fill, it was decided to remove the silt prior to construction.

The silt removal was carried out by a large back-actor dredger. The back-actor was selected due to the depth of silt and the difficult access to some areas. Some 70,000m³ of silt was removed from site in hopper barges and dumped at sea in a licensed disposal area. A cutter suction dredger was used to dredge the fill material from within the fairway area and to pump the material into the reclamation area through a floating pipeline. Almost 185,000m³ of fill material was pumped into an area enclosed by the steel sheet pile wall, the rock embankment and the existing shoreline. Hydraulically placed fill contains a high proportion of water and this was drained back into the Harbour through silt boxes.

Because the Harbour Wall was not completed to full height before filling commenced and because of the need to install tie rods to anchor the steel sheet pile wall at low water level, the filling was carried out in three stages. The first stage involved filling the whole area up to about low water level. The second stage involved building up bunds, using the silty sand material, running behind the rock embankment and behind the anchor walls as shown in Figure 6. This bunded area was then filled to about 4 metres above finished level. This had the advantage of surcharging the underlying fill and therefore accelerating consolidation. The third stage involved regrading the fill to finished levels.

4.5 Bankseat.

The bankseat forms the abutment for the HSS linkspan as shown in Figure 7. The linkspan is described below and provides a mooring point for the HSS carrier. Wind loading on the HSS carrier produces longitudinal corner loads of about $\pm 4,500\text{kN}$ and lateral loads of about 2,000kN at the bankseat bearings. These loads require a substantial foundation.

A number of foundation options were considered including a suspended reinforced concrete deck on vertical and raking tubular steel piles and a reinforced concrete gravity structure consisting of a large sand filled 'tray'. The most economic option was a reinforced concrete relieving platform and abutment wall founded on a number of box piles incorporated in the anchored steel sheet pile retaining wall and a number of vertical tubular steel bearing piles. The relieving platform was horizontally restrained by steel tie rods to a combined anchor wall for the tie rods from the sheet pile retaining wall.

Figure 6 - Land Reclamation

The large couple due to the wind load on the HSS carrier was resisted by passive soil pressure on one half of the bankseat, tie roads on the other half and by wall friction and the lateral stiffness of the bearing piles and box piles. The design envisaged the improvement of the hydraulically placed silty sand fill by vibro-compaction in order to provide the required soil resistance. However tests on the sand fill after placing showed that the soil had sufficient strength without the need for additional improvement, other than the thorough compaction of the fill above low water level.

The bankseat has reinforced earth wing walls to retain the sand fill forming a ramp between the marshalling area and the linkspan road deck. The ramp consists of a reinforced concrete road slab with a vertical profile to suit smooth transitions for vehicles. The wing walls are capped with substantial parapet walls to contain vehicles.

The bankseat also provides a foundation for four reinforced concrete bridge piers supporting the passenger walkway and the shore end of the passenger gangways on the linkspan. Substantial plinths are provided between each pair of bridge piers to support two linkspan jacking frames.

The sheet pile wall forming the bankseat is protected by a substantial rock armour scour blanket to resist erosion by the powerful water jets on the HSS carrier.

The bankseat design has proved to be very economical and has been adopted at other HSS terminals.

4.6 Site Services.

An extensive network of pipes and ducts was laid under the paved areas to provide the necessary site services. The HSS is to be bunkered at Holyhead. However the services were designed to accommodate site requirements and also HSS loads in emergency.

Surface Water: Some 1600m of concrete pipes from 150mm to 375mm dia. were laid in four separate runs discharging to sea via 'Tideflex' non-return valves. The paved areas were provided with surface water gulleys connected to the network. Oil interceptor tanks were provided at the end of each line.

Foul Sewage: A 30 l/s duplicate submersible pumping station was provided within the site discharging via 200mm ductile iron rising main to the public sewer. Some 250m of uPVC drainage pipes ranging from 100mm to 150mm dia. were laid to transfer flows to the station.

Potable Water: The potable water demand was calculated at 510m³/d and 250m of 100mm and 150mm dia. ductile iron main were laid within the site from the public main to storage tanks located within the buildings. Storage capacity equivalent to one day's supply was provided.

Fire Fighting: As the local supply available from the public mains was inadequate for fire fighting purposes a sea water fire fighting system was installed. Three submersible pumps complete with cathodically protected anti-fouling passive intake screens were provided, suspended from St. Michael's Pier. A dedicated fire main network consisting of 200mm and 300mm ductile iron pipes was installed and 8 hydrants fitted at strategic locations around the site. The pumping capacity is 180 l/s and the system is designed to give in excess of 0.7 bar pressure at a flow of 90 l/s at the last hydrant.

Gas: An 80mm dia. MDPE supply main was provided within the site from the public road to boiler locations within the buildings.

Power Supply: The original power supply to the port came from a 10kVA sub-station located in the Customs Building.

As this was being demolished a new 840KVA sub-station was constructed within the underground car-park. The preservation of a permanent supply to the existing operations on St. Michael's Pier and the changeover to the new installation posed particular programme difficulties for the Contractor during construction.

Site Lighting: The site lighting was designed to be as low as possible to minimise nuisance for local residents. Accordingly, 9m high twin head lights mounted on 1m high concrete columns were adopted in the marshalling and road areas. Elsewhere a variety of feature lights were used. A network of 100mm uPVC ducts was laid to facilitate cabling.

Ducts: Additional ducting was laid to cater for data communications, CCTV systems and telephone lines.

4.7 Pavement Design.

The road and marshalling areas consist primarily of two pavement types, marshall asphalt and concrete brick paviors.

Marshall asphalt covers the area between the edge of Harbour Road and the Porte Cochere including coach/taxi drop-off areas and car-parking areas and is approximately 8,000m² in area. Pavements subject to loads from heavy goods vehicles were constructed with a Clause 804 sub-base underlying 200mm of lean mix concrete prior to topping with a dense bitumen macadam base coarse and marshall asphalt wearing course. In areas of lighter traffic such as the public car-park, the lean mix base was not required but a depth increase in the Clause 804 sub-base was used.

Within the port itself, which is all on hydraulically placed sand fill, marshalling areas have been constructed in 80mm thick concrete brick paviors, complying with BS 6717, on a sand bedding. The road pavement make-up below this is identical to that for the heavily trafficked areas in marshall asphalt. Approximately 15,000m² of paviors have been laid. The paved areas

are provided with extensive standard and Trieff kerbs forming roadways and traffic islands.

5. LINKSPAN.

5.1 Design Concept for HSS Linkspan.

The HSS linkspan concept is unusual. The linkspan provides both a vehicular and passenger traffic link between the HSS carrier and the shore and a mooring system for the HSS carrier. At conventional ferry berths and at berths for the smaller wave piercing catamaran ferries, vessels are berthed against fenders and moored by lines to bollards on dolphins or piers. Vehicles are normally carried on a shore ro-ro ramp between the ferry and the shore and the ferry is usually provided with its own ship ramp, which rests on the shore ro-ro ramp. Passengers are carried either on a separate passenger gangway or on a gangway supported on the shore ramp.

The HSS linkspan has five traffic lanes in order to assist the rapid loading and unloading of vehicles. The central lane is reserved for servicing the HSS carrier. Conventional shore ro-ro ramps have only one or two lanes. The HSS linkspan is almost as wide as the HSS carrier and has a fendering and mooring system at its outer end to 'clamp' the carrier. The HSS linkspan is supported on bearings at the shore end and on a semi-submersible pontoon at the ship end, except when 'clamped' on the HSS, when applied loads are supported on the stern of the ship.

The HSS linkspan also has two passenger gangways supported at high level above the road deck on columns at the outer end and on bearings on the top of reinforced concrete bridge piers at the shore end.

The loads on the HSS carrier are transmitted through the bearings to the bankseat when the carrier is 'clamped' to the linkspan. This results in relatively high loads on the bankseat, particularly from wind loads on the HSS carrier.

5.2 Installation of HSS Linkspan.

The HSS linkspan was delivered on a large flat top barge. The passenger gangways were assembled onto their bearings at the outer end of the linkspan and the complete structure was then lifted off the barge by a large floating 'shear leg' crane, transported to the berth and lowered onto its bearings on the bankseat. Shore based mobile cranes lifted the inshore end of the passenger gangways onto their bearings. The pontoon and stub columns were floated underneath the linkspan and bolted to the columns at the outer end of the bridge. The pontoon was then ballasted and the floating crane released.

The bearings at road deck and gangway level on the bankseat had to be accurately fixed in position and carefully surveyed in order to achieve the successful installation of the linkspan. Following the initial installation the bearings were grouted in and the holding down bolts tightened.

The hydraulic systems for adjusting the level of the linkspan and for mooring the HSS carrier were then connected and tested, prior to trial operations with the HSS carrier. The maiden voyage of the HSS is scheduled to take place in March 1996.

6. TERMINAL BUILDINGS.

6.1 Existing Buildings.

Up to the commencement of the new project Stena had access to two berths at St. Michael's Pier. A conventional ferry docked to the west of the pier, with the Sea Lynx Catamaran docking on the east side. A two-storey terminal building constructed in the late 1960s was used for passenger movements on and off both ferries, and also for office space for the Harbour Police. This building, with a floor area of about 1,500m² was located on the pier and comprised a reinforced concrete frame of floor slabs, beams and columns. It was linked via a concrete underground passenger walkway to an entry-point on Harbour Road. The building was functional in nature, with no appreciable architectural merit. A survey of the building indicated that the structural frame was in good condition.

In addition to the existing terminal building the site also contained a Customs Building with offices for Stena and the Harbour Master and an office and information centre for Dublin Tourism. It was considered that these buildings could not be retained as part of the new project due to their location and lack of aesthetic merit.

Figure 7 - Section Through Bankseat & Linkspan

Figure 8 - Terminal Building Floor Plan

6.2 New Terminal Design.

The new terminal was designed such that it would be a fitting gateway for Ireland's largest passenger port. Conceptually it was to link the theme of seafaring with the landbase.

The building has a floor area of 7,100m² and it contains the following principal features:

- Main Arrivals/Departures Hall
- Restaurant
- Departures Lounge
- Arrivals Hall

- Baggage Reclaim Hall
- Tourist Information Office
- Ticket and Administration Offices

The building has the principal function of allowing controlled and safe movement of passengers on and from the HSS. It has been designed to accommodate two separate streams of movement.

Departing passengers check-in in the ground floor Departures Hall as shown in Figure 8. The check-in procedure is identical to that used in air travel, with baggage taken from passengers and transported by truck to the ship.

Passengers then advance to the first floor Departures Lounge, passing over the vehicle underpass and beside the Restaurant. When the HSS is ready for embarkation the passengers move to the second floor, through the Passenger Walkways and onto the vessel.

Arriving passengers take a different route through the building. Disembarkation is through the Passenger Walkways and onto the second floor Arrivals Hall. Passengers descend immediately to the first floor and then to the ground floor Baggage Hall. Here baggage is returned using a similar conveyor system to airports. Passengers then exit into the ground floor Arrivals Hall and leave the building.

Since the foot passenger embarkation/disembarkation point is about 8m above ground level it is necessary to move people through these levels in the building. A staircase, escalator and lift is provided at each change in level, allowing for passenger mobility and full disabled access. The building allows disabled users to move unaccompanied from the entrance at ground level to the ship.

In the event of fire, emergency exits and staircases allow for safe movement out of the building. This is achieved through the use of two dedicated fire exit staircases with a flight width of 2.6m, in addition to the other normal-use staircases. Lifts can be used by disabled passengers in the event of fire through the provision of fire compartments at the lift lobbies.

The building has a sophisticated CCTV security system which is monitored and controlled in a central control room.

6.3 Demolitions.

A substantial amount of demolition was required at the start of the project. About 20% of the existing building terminal floor

Figure 9 - Section Through Pier & Terminal Building

Figure 10 - Refurbishment of Existing Terminal

area was removed at its south end to allow for linking the old building with the new. A helical staircase with a circular concrete wall was demolished at the north end of the building. Local pockets of existing structure were also removed to accommodate a new lift shaft and a new escalator and staircase. This work required a substantial amount of temporary support-work and led to close liaison between the project structural engineer and the demolition sub-contractor.

The old Customs Building with Stena and Harbour Master offices was demolished completely without any difficulty. The Tourist Office was retained by the Contractor as a site office until close to the end of the project and was then demolished.

Localised sections of the pier were also broken out. This was principally to allow new piles to be placed at the south end of the pier to support new columns in the building. Boring of existing RC beams under the existing pier was carried out to fit new water and drainage pipes serving the new building.

With the site cleared of all redundant buildings the Contractor was in a position to proceed with the construction of the new building.

6.4 Refurbishment.

The refurbishment of the old building (see Figure 9) and its incorporation into the new Terminal proved to be one of the most interesting aspects of the structural engineering input. The existing building on the pier required an extension upwards in the form of a second floor, an extension to the south to link with the new building and an extension to the west to provide new space in the first floor Departures lounge.

The existing beams were substantial in size with an overall depth of 750mm. Cores were taken from the beams and

columns and tested and the concrete was identified as having a characteristic compressive strength of 30N/mm². The Department of the Marine supplied reinforcement drawings for the structure which showed mild steel rebar. Structural analysis identified a superimposed load capacity of around 2.5kN/m² for the longitudinal floor beams.

The second floor was developed from the roof of the old building. The reinforced concrete structure to this roof was similar in form and capacity to the first floor below.

The new walls and roof for the second floor were formed by structural steel portal frames at 3.8m centres as shown in Figure 10. This steelwork is exposed and comprises light universal beam sections. The portal rafters are curved to three varying radii, the most common being 14.3m. A profiled steel deck is used to span between the rafters and the roof is finished using a Kal Zip curved aluminium roofing material. Fixing of the portal frame bases was achieved using chemical anchor bolts in holes drilled in

the existing concrete beams. This involved extensive trial drilling to avoid existing reinforcement. The problem was eased by using a base plate with a slotted hole combined with an adjustable washer with a circular hole. The washer was keyed and welded to the base plate allowing a tolerance of up to 30mm in placing the chemical anchors.

The refurbished building was designed for a superimposed floor load capacity of 5.0kN/m². In addition new dead load capacity was required in some beams to resist loads from new external and internal walls.

Consequently most of the existing longitudinal floor beams were under capacity for the new loading conditions. Moment capacity increases of 30 - 40% were required at mid-spans allowing for hinge formation at supports. Strengthening options were limited due to the beams carrying narrow slab widths and having long spans (7.62m) between cross-frames. Accordingly, division of the slab spans with structural steel was not considered a viable option. Plate bonding techniques were considered but discounted due to the low strength increase achievable and due to fire protection requirements. The strengthening technique designed involved the bolting of steel plates -120mm deep x 5mm thick x 5.5m long to both sides of beams using chemical anchors. Plates were not attached to the beam soffits due to reinforcement congestion concerns and very low ceiling heights. The technique was tested by DIT, Bolton Street, with larger scale tests undertaken by Forbairt, Glasnevin as shown in Figure 11. The load/deflection curves in Figure 12 indicate beam stiffness and ultimate strength increases up to 140% as a result of plating.

At the south end of the existing building a completely new structure was built to

Figure 11 - Testing of Plated Beam

Figure 12 - Beam Plating Graph

replace a large area of demolition. Demolition finished at an expansion joint and this joint was maintained at the edge of the new construction. The new structure consists of ground, first and second floors, with an intermediate floor under a section of the first floor for plant. The structure is a reinforced concrete frame, with stability provided by a concrete lift shaft and concrete walls. New 457mm diameter by 16mm thick tubular steel piles were required to support 20 new RC columns in this area. To drive these piles, openings were made in the existing concrete wharf deck and the piles were driven to set in the stiff boulder clay overlying rock. RC pile caps were cast at the pile heads and dowelled into the wharf slab.

The roof to this section of the building is nominally flat and constructed of steel beams, cold rolled steel purlins, a steel deck and insulation covered with a Trocal membrane. The link between the refurbished building and the new building is in the form of a bridge with a 5.0m clearance under which traffic can pass in both directions as shown in Figure 13. With a 12m span forming the restaurant area, the bridge consists of a 550 deep ribbed reinforced concrete slab supported at each end by RC beams and columns.

6.5 New Arrivals/Departures Facilities.

The new Arrivals/Departures Building has a floor area of about 3000m². It is principally a reinforced concrete structure comprising a flat steel roof, supported by RC columns, a first floor constructed of RC slabs and beams and a ground floor formed by RC ground beams supported by piles. Lateral stability to the structure is provided by RC shear walls and lift shafts. All staircases were constructed of reinforced concrete. The granite-clad wall on the east elevation is constructed of reinforced concrete and designed as a

vertically spanning panel propped at the top by the roof.

The foundations consist of piles and ground beams. The site investigations reported loose granite boulders as fill material overlying rock, varying in depth from 3m to 13m. To penetrate the boulders reinforced concrete piles were specified, at 5m centres generally. In some areas the Contractor experienced difficulty in containing the grout for the piles. A solution which involved filling predrilled holes with gravel and driving steel H-piles was adopted. Piles generally had a working load of between 600 and 1000 kN.

6.6 Passenger Walkways.

Foot passengers transfer on and from the HSS via high-level walkways. The total walkway length is 67.2m, divided into two spans of 24.9m and one span of 17.4m. Walkways 1 and 2, as shown in Figure 14, are both 4.0m wide with 2.4 floor to ceiling height, have a 150mm deep reinforced concrete floor, on steel beams. The steel beams are supported by Warren Trusses on either side with a steel truss also forming the roof. Walkway 3 is 5.0m wide, with a 150mm reinforced concrete floor on universal steel column sections. These sections are supported by a Vierendeel Truss on either side, with a steel roof. Each walkway resists lateral load by a portal action of the side and roof members. The walkway structures have a 30 minute fire rating achieved by an intumescent paint system. There are four supports to the walkway structures, two steel structures, with braced circular hollow section columns and two reinforced concrete structures. The concrete structures are located on the bankseat and in addition to supporting the walkways they provide resistance to lateral loads imposed by the linkspan at walkway level as described earlier.

6.7 Building Services System - Mechanical and Electrical Services.

Extensive and modern building services, transportation and baggage handling systems were incorporated into the new Terminal Building.

A study of the ventilation requirements for the various public areas indicated that, due to the short time occupancy of the Arrivals/Baggage Reclaim area and the large volume of the Main Concourse and Baggage Check-in area, controlled mechanical ventilation only was required for these areas. The Departures Lounge and Restaurant were fully air conditioned. Variable speed drives were installed on the plant serving these areas, controlled by air quality sensors. At times of low occupancy, the plant runs at a low speed, with resultant energy savings.

A comprehensive CCTV and token Operated Door Access System were installed for security purposes. The two systems are interlinked via automatic call-up of cameras when controlled doors are used by unauthorised personnel.

A Building Management System is provided to control and monitor the mechanical services plant and the lighting systems. It also monitors the sewage pumping stations in the Harbour, designed by P.H. McCarthy & Partners some two years previously, and has been designed to co-ordinate plant operation and lighting control with sailing times, with the facility for manual override to cater for possible delays due to weather. The design also allows for remote monitoring and control by the Harbour Manager if required in the future.

A computer-controlled Variable Message System has been installed in all internal public areas and in the external traffic standage area to provide sailing information for the passengers. The system will be extended to the Motorists'

Figure 13 - Section Through Underpass

Figure 14 - Passenger Walkway

Facilities Building, at present under 7. construction.

7. CIVIC AND AMENITY FEATURES.

7.1 Public Plaza and Car-Park.

A fire safety engineering approach was adopted for the building with fire hose-reels and extinguishers for the first-aid fire-fighting and external hydrants supplied with sea water using three submersible pumps. An addressable automatic fire detection system was provided, linked to the public address/voice evacuation system. The CCTV system was also designed as an aid for the security staff in the evacuation of the building. Emergency exit doors in the public areas were connected to the door access control system and these are automatically disconnected if a fire occurs.

A single storey car-park was constructed immediately to the east of the new Terminal Building, with the Public Plaza as the roof. Existing site levels allowed for a change in level from the Harbour Road grade to a level 3m lower, to allow for access to the car-park. The covered structure has space for 62 cars and also houses an ESB sub-station, electrical switch room and air-handling plant room.

The Plaza deck is constructed of precast hollow core slabs with a maximum span of 7m, topped with a structural concrete screed.

To facilitate foot passengers, baggage is now handled as in an airport. Baggage check-in conveyors and two reclaim carousels have been installed along with the associated equipment and data cabling for baggage tagging and ticket verification. The system has been designed and cabled to allow for further ticket verification at the check-in gates.

6.8 Ancillary Buildings.

The Customs Vehicle Turning-Out Building is a facility in which Customs can unload, strip-out or hold suspect vehicles and is sized to accommodate one Heavy Goods Vehicle. It is a structural steel portal frame building, with curved rafters, in the style of the refurbished terminal building. Foundations consist of reinforced concrete ground beams. The building is piled using 457mm diameter tubular steel piles, through the sand fill material onto the underlying boulder clay.

The crescent-shaped Motorists' building is a single-storey reinforced concrete structure with a floor area of 270m² approximately. The sea wall forms the curved seaward perimeter of the building, while precast concrete slabs and RC beams and columns comprise the rest of the structure. The foundations consist of a base slab, which also provides stability to the sea wall and which is supported on tubular steel piles.

The 200mm deep precast units are supported by reinforced concrete inverted T-shaped beams, which in turn are supported by RC columns. Two sides of the building are substantially open to the weather, with 300mm thick RC retaining walls on the other two sides.

The car-park ground floor slab is a 300mm thick flat slab, support at pile-head locations, with a maximum panel size of 7.9m x 7.9m. Piles were grouped

in twos and threes, with a working load of 600kN to 1000kN. Pile depth varied from 3m to 9.5m. The piling was similar to that used in the main Terminal Building foundations.

The Design Team selected a variety of concrete finishes for the Public Plaza/car-park. The RC wall which defines two sides of the Plaza is bush-hammered on the terminal side and constructed with a ribbed finish on the seaward side. The ribbed finish is formed using site fabricated formwork. A curved wall which forms a water feature area has a board-marked concrete finish. The plaza is finished in a carefully designed pattern of Blanc de Bierge, Tegula and natural limestone paving which extends across the front of the main Terminal Building. Artistic features include a tiled serpentine seat and a specially commissioned sculpture.

7.2 Porte Cochere.

The Porte Cochere or Carriage Entrance delineates the vehicle entrance to the port. To accommodate rapid entry for vehicles there are 6 car lanes and 4 truck lanes with ticket check-in facilities. The canopy to this area consists of 2 tented structures. The car check-in structure has plan dimensions of 25m x 7m and a

Figure 15 - Port Cochere

clear height of 4m as shown in Figure 15. The truck check-in structure has dimensions of 60m x 8m with 5m clearance.

The larger structure has 7 spans, the longest being 12.16m. The complete structure is supported by 6 steel circular hollow 273 x 6.3mm sections. Each post is supported obliquely by a 168.3 x 6.3mm circular hollow section. There are 4 spans in the car ticket canopy structure, the longest being 7.0m. This

VOLUME OF SILT REMOVAL	70,000m ³
VOLUME OF SAND FILL FROM HARBOUR	185,000m ³
RECLAMATION AREA	15,000m ²
RECLAMATION BUND LENGTH	215m
IMPORTED ROCK VOLUME	55,000m ³
SHEET PILE WEIGHT	1,600t
MAIN SHEET PILE WALL LENGTH	210m
PAVING	30,000m ²
UNDERGROUND PIPES & SERVICES	5,000m
TERMINAL BUILDING FLOOR AREA	7,100m ²
PASSENGER WALKWAY LENGTH	67m
CIVIC DECK/CAR PARK AREA	1,650m ²
CONCRETE VOLUME	14,000m ³
REINFORCING STEEL WEIGHT	800t
STRUCTURAL STEEL WEIGHT	300t
ALUMINIUM CLADDING ON BUILDING	3,000m ²
GLASS AREA IN BUILDING	700m ²
GRANITE CLADDING ON BUILDING	400m ²

Figure 16 - Leading Quantities

structure is supported by 3 posts of identical size to the larger structure.

The fabric is a PVC-coated high density polyfibre yarn with a fluor-polymer lacquer outer coating and is stretched over the steel structure. Galvanised steel cables are incorporated into the fabric along its edges and these are tensioned to hold the fabric to its shape. Steel connector plates are also incorporated in the fabric at connections, where stresses are greatest. Primary overall stability is provided by moment connections between the column base plates and reinforced concrete foundations. These provide lateral stability in both directions.

At each post there are 4 horizontal pinned members located at right angles to each other. At the extremity of each post location, stainless steel cables are used as ties to resist wind uplift forces.

The overall effect is to provide a spectacular structure at the entrance to the port which provides a definition to the boundary of the vehicle marshalling and the secure port area.

7.3 Promenade.

A new public Promenade and sea wall have been constructed along the west perimeter of the site. Beginning adjacent to the Royal Irish Yacht Club, the 4.0m wide promenade was constructed to the rear of the perimeter concrete sea defence. A new reinforced concrete wave wall 2.1m in height forms the site boundary between the public Promenade and the Terminal site.

7.4 Soft Landscaping.

The major concentration of soft landscape is along the southern edge of the site which will act as a green buffer zone between the development and the existing urban edge along Harbour Road.

Tree and shrub species were selected on the basis of their wind resistance and tolerance to salt spray, as well as their functional characteristics. Of particular interest is the inclusion of ten *Trachycarpus Excelsior* or palm feature trees in a cluster to the front of the main Terminal Building.

8. CONCLUSION.

The £22M Dun Laoghaire Harbour Ferry Terminal Development is a unique project not alone in catering for existing and new shipping technology but also in the sensitive integration of a major port complex into an existing urban environment. The project presented a major challenge for the Department of the Marine and their Consultants and involved extensive interfacing with Stena Line and their advisors in order to cater fully for the new revolutionary service. The programme constraints were onerous and were only achieved through excellent teamwork with the assistance of information technology. The breadth and scope of the works made this a truly multi-disciplinary project. It is a tribute to the Contractors employed that the highest standards were achieved despite extreme time pressure. More importantly there was no serious accident or injury during the works.

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